

Electrifying the Future of Urban Mobility

Recommendations for Bus Electrification

KEY MESSAGES

- While Australian electricity Distribution Network Service Providers (DNSPs) are conducting the price review for the next five-year regulatory period, the significant shift in the electrification of transportation, specifically bus electric vehicles associated with public transportation, should be considered. In addition to the increase in energy demand, the potential locations of charging stations, along with the opportunity for these “mobile batteries” to support the low voltage network, is important for estimating proposed infrastructure upgrades and the associated costs. A joint committee of electricity and transport sectors is recommended to address the problem.
- Bus operators require a comprehensive business model for charging of Battery Electric Buses (BEBs) that considers depot, terminal, and possibly en-route charging. There are several technologies to reduce both capital and operational costs of the charging process as well as making it clean, such as smart charging, battery-buffered charging, and public sharing of charging facilities.
- BEBs can also support the electricity market through V2G, or contribute to compensate the minimum demand reduction through daytime charging. To this end, bus operators need to be engaged with the electricity sector, especially DNSPs.
- Mass uptake of BEBs requires significant increases in digital communications for buses, depots, charging stations, and operating centres. The readiness of the IT infrastructure of bus operators should be revisited.

BACKGROUND

While the main debates on the transport electrification are focused on electrifying light vehicles, BEBs have shown the potential and proven technology to contribute to transport decarbonisation [1]. Transport electrification will be one of the main challenges for transport authorities during the next decade as it sits at the intersection of transportation and electricity sectors. Despite shorter range and lower passenger capacity compared to internal combustion engine (ICE)-based buses, BEBs have to deliver a reliable mobility service while their interaction with the electricity network for charging should be managed.

Bus electrification in Australia has been started by setting up the aims and running trials in different states. In general, fleet electrification, including buses, is subject to the following main challenges:

- planning and installing charging infrastructure;
- charging scheduling, optimal location and size of chargers;
- comprehensive business model; and
- higher purchase cost of BEBs compared to ICE, although it will drop over time.

To address the challenges and opportunities of transport electrification in buses, RMIT University in collaboration with the Centre for New Energy Technologies (C4NET) and the iMOVE CRC have held two *Conductor Series*

The NT Government investigate the feasibility of trialling Zero Emission Buses (ZEBs) in the urban fleet.

An BEB trial commenced in Perth in February 2022. Joint Federal and State Governments' program to locally manufacture 130 buses and the charging infrastructure is ongoing. A feasibility study for "Electric School Buses" is running.

In Dec 2022:

- The first BEB began operating on the Adelaide Metro network.
- A tender for Feasibility Studies and Business Cases for the Transition to Zero Emission Public Transport was released.

In mid-2022, TAS announced plans to conduct zero emission bus trials (starting late 2023).

- Opened Australia's first all-electric bus depot in April 2022.
- All new buses will be zero emission from 2025 in Southeast QLD, and from 2025-2030 across regional area.
- Brisbane City Council is investing in 60 new BEBs.

- 8,000+ buses will all be ZEB by 2047. The transition will be complete in Greater Sydney by 2035, in Outer Metropolitan regions by 2040, and in Regional NSW by 2047.
- The ACT is targeting a 100% zero emissions bus fleet by 2040.
- The Government has commenced a three-year Zero Emissions Bus Trial with 52 ZEBs.
- The Government's goal to achieve net zero emissions by 2045.
- Victoria will only purchase zero emission buses from 2025.
- Victoria aims to have 87 BEBs by 2025 in the public fleet.

events in November 2022 and May 2023. These events concluded that both transport and electricity sectors need to take actions, either joint or separately, to ensure smooth integration of BEBs into the transport system and the power grid. The discussions in those meetings, aligned with the international literature and practice reviews, are summarised in this White Paper.

CHARGING DEMAND OF BEBs

Australian distribution network service providers (DNSPs) conduct a price review process every five years to set electricity prices with the Australian Energy Regulator (AER). For example, the current period will end in 2025 in Victoria. Thus, DNSPs are starting to prepare their proposal for the next period 2026–2031. Significant BEB uptake is expected during this period. Thus,

1. The transport sector should provide an estimate of the "amount of required energy" and "location/ amount of the required power" for BEB charging.
2. DNSPs should review this requirement, finalise it in collaboration with the transport sector, and reflect it in the price review.

Reflection of the charging demand of bus electrification in the electricity price review is an urgent action and requires a committee of DNSPs and transport planners. Relevant departments of the state governments, such as the Victorian Department of Energy, Environment and Climate Action (DEECA), may facilitate the governance of

this action, however it is noted the DNSPs are regulated by the Australian Energy Regulator (AER). In addition, depot peak charging may coincide with the peak electricity demand in the grid. Policies and regulations, such as introducing a cap on consumption, are required especially during evening time to prevent disruption of depot charging on grid stability.

PLANNING AND OPERATION OF BEBs

The upfront cost of fleet and charging infrastructure

Bus operators and transport authorities can reduce the significant capital costs of replacing old ICE-based buses with BEBs and electrification of bus depots to charge them.

- a. *Optimising BEB battery sizes and charging stations:* Battery capacities of BEBs typically vary between 150kWh and 400kWh today, while higher capacities

are expected in future [2]. Purchasing BEBs with appropriate battery sizes that match the route and the required schedule, results in efficient investment and also facilitates operational aspects, e.g., faster charging. Some tools, such as RouteZero developed by the Australian National University (ANU) and ZENOBE, can help bus operators more precisely assess charging needs, e.g., through trials and projects such as the assessment of charging requirements for Melbourne's electric bus fleet [3].

b. *Realistic peak demand calculation for depots:* Due to internal battery management systems, BEBs are often not charged at the maximum charger rating during the whole charging process. Thus, for example, a bus depot with 20 units of 350kW chargers does not require a 7MW (20 x 350kWh) substation to be fed. In addition, a curtailment factor should be defined for each bus depot. This factor defines a limit on the number of buses that can be charged simultaneously without affecting mobility services and the power capacity of the depot. For example, a study on a depot with 127 buses in Hamburg, Germany, showed that a curtailment factor of 0.54 is appropriate if the charging is on-demand [4]. This factor can be calculated for each depot based on the operation schedule of BEBs, their battery sizes, capacity of chargers, and other practical and operational limitations.

Updating bus timetable planning

Australian ZEB trials to date have shown that BEBs rarely need daytime charging. However, international practices, see, e.g., [2], still suggests charging possibility during the day to support BEB operations and to benefit from clean charging. This can be done either through opportunistic charging in selected bus stops or through fast chargers in terminals. Bus schedules may need to be revised, considering the timetabled trips, locations of recharging

stations, and the required charging time. There is always a trade-off between choosing BEBs with larger battery sizes; and investing in more numerous chargers in certain bus stops and terminals. The problem should be addressed at different BEB penetration levels, while operators deal with a mixed BEB and ICE-based bus fleet.

MANAGING THE CHARGING COST

Bus operators require a comprehensive business model for electric energy management to consider the full capacity of the charging infrastructure.

Green charging

Night-time depot charging is likely the easiest way to charge EBs, but not the cleanest and cheapest way. Bus operators may maximise clean daytime charging in the BEB schedule, which also reduces the charging cost of BEBs. Technologies such as ultra-fast opportunity chargers for en-route charging and microgrid-based solutions for green charging in depots and bus station are available. Some of these technologies are being trialled in ARENA's Next Generation Electric Bus Depot project [6].

Smart charging

Managing the demand for charging in depots and main bus stations can reduce the upgrade cost of electrical infrastructure, as well as shifting or distributing the demand over off-peak time, thus saving in electricity bills for bus operators. Combining smart and green charging solutions will result in more savings.

Providing services to the grid

The transport sector needs to be well-engaged with the DNSPs for the requirements to contribute to the electricity market. This contribution can be done through daytime charging to partially compensate the so-called "minimum demand reduction" problem, selling electricity to the grid in the peak times through V2G, or supporting vulnerable network in far regional areas.

Public sharing of charging facilities

Bus operators can plan to share their charging infrastructure (in depots and bus stops) with other organisations during mobility off-peak times. A good example is the rapid charging centre of First Bus, a bus operator in Glasgow, UK, where transport, energy, and finance sectors come together to make the best use investment [5]. Charging facilities, which allow 150 buses to be charged at one time, are shared with other organisations that operate in the city and also with third-party businesses during the day, when buses are out in service.

IT SYSTEM UPGRADE

Data centre

Data collected from trials can help transport and energy sectors as well as research institutes and universities to better analyse the challenges such as:

- EB operation, planning, and required investment;
- smart and green charging infrastructure;
- battery degradation; and
- battery recycling and reuse possibilities.

The recent National EV strategy includes initiatives for recycling, reuse and stewardship for EV and other large format batteries [7]. A data centre and national standards on collecting, storing, and sharing data from trials would facilitate the access of all stakeholders to data for research purposes.

Control centre upgrade

Planning and monitoring of BEB charging requires accurate estimates on the arrival and departure times of buses and the amount of required energy. It also requires a communication network with centralised and distributed charging facilities. Advanced optimisation algorithms, able to assign appropriate charging blocks and parking positions to each BEB and preconditioning activities, are required to manage the charging process. That may in turn require a significant upgrade in the IT system of bus depots and the bus operators' infrastructure.

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